

The Influence of Compensation, Work Discipline, and Work Environment on Employee Performance through Work Motivation as a Variable Intervening on J&T Express Sampang District Area

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to examine the performance of employees at J&T Express in the Sampang District Region by analyzing the influence of compensation, work discipline, and work environment on employee performance through work motivation as a mediation. The approach taken is quantitative research, which aims to verify hypotheses determined by the researcher. The research method applied in this study is a survey in the form of a questionnaire. The population in this study consists of subjects related to the research conducted at J&T Express in the Sampang District Region, and the respondents of this research are employees of J&T Express in the Sampang District Region. 120 respondents were found using the saturated sampling technique. Hypothesis testing in this research was conducted using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) based on Partial Least Square (PLS). Based on the analysis results of 10 hypotheses, it was found that 8 hypotheses were accepted and significant, while the other 2 were rejected and not significant. From these results, it was found that the compensation variable (X1) and work motivation (Z) have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, while the work discipline variable (X2) and work environment (X3) have no significant effect on employee performance. Then, the compensation variable (X1), work discipline (X2), and work environment (X3) have a positive and significant effect on work motivation (Z). Furthermore, for the indirect effect, the influence of variables X (compensation, work discipline, and work environment) on employee performance (Y) through work motivation (Z) has a positive and significant effect.

KEYWORDS: compensation, discipline, environment, motivation, performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Goods delivery services or expedition services are now increasingly in demand by people in Indonesia, especially in this sophisticated era. Technological advances in the era of globalization tend to make people like everything that is easy and practical. In Indonesia, there are many delivery service companies that are believed to have high quality with various forms of delivery services that make it easier for customers to choose services that suit their needs. One of the delivery services that is in demand is the company PT. Global Jet Express, hereinafter referred to as J&T EXPRESS

According to Google survey results (2023), J&T Express is the second most popular expedition after JNE. With a search percentage of 21.5% above SI Cepat, POS Indonesia and TIKI, it shows that J&T is an expedition service company with good performance. However, J&T Express's Google business rating in Sampang Regency is mostly not that high, even below 3. The complaints that most often arise are related to packages not being sent on time (53%), couriers still charging fees (31%), couriers not delivering packages according to the delivery address (11%) and other reasons related to the courier's responsible attitude and goods. not arriving and other things related to customer dissatisfaction with the services provided by J&T Express couriers (9%), so this can reflect the quality of human resources or employee performance at the J&T Express company.

Previous experts or researchers said that there are several things that can influence employee performance, namely. The first is compensation, Mangkunegara (2013) revealed that the compensation given to employees greatly influences the level of job satisfaction and work motivation as well as work results. Second is the work environment. According to H. Wijaya & Susanty (2017), the work environment is everything around the employee that influences him in carrying out and completing the tasks given to him in an area. Lastly is work discipline, Widiyanti (2022:243) states that work discipline is an important thing that needs to be paid attention to and should not be left to chance. Because, there are various positive reasons why work discipline needs to be maintained.

So from the three opinions above we can obtain a gap in the relationship between variables, namely the relationship between compensation, work discipline and work environment with work motivation and the relationship between all variables and

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performance. This research will examine the influence of compensation factors, work environment and work discipline on work motivation and their impact on the performance of J&T Express couriers with the aim of obtaining factors that significantly need to be improved to increase courier work motivation which in turn can improve the performance of J&T Express couriers in the Sampang area.

II. THEORETICAL STUDY

A. Human Resource Management

According to Arif Yusuf Hamali (2018, 2) states that human resource management is a strategic approach to skills, motivation, development and management of resource organization and this opinion is reinforced by Prasadja Ricardianto (2018, 15) by saying that resource management Human resources is a science or method of how to manage the relationships and roles of resources (workforce) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the shared (goal) of the company, employees and society is maximized.

B. Theory AMO

The AMO theory first appeared by Vroom (1964) which was quoted by Blumberg & Pringle (1982) and adopted an interactive relationship by considering ability and motivation, and explaining performance with the function $P = f(A \times M)$ (AL-Mottahar & Pangil, 2021). Then. Along with the development of time and science. AMO theory reaches the latest update that effort *discretionary* employees with three components, namely: employees must have the necessary skills, employees need motivation, and there is support from the right superiors to give employees the opportunity to participate with their organization (Marin Garcia & Tomas, 2016). Based on this model, the concept can be described *high performance work system* (HPWS) which was later developed by Appelbaum (2000), and represents three elements that can improve employee performance: individual ability (A), motivation (M), and opportunity to participate (O) (Marin-Garcia & Tomas, 2016).

C. Compensation

According to Enny (2019:37), compensation is a form of reciprocal service provided to employees as a form of appreciation for their contribution and work to the organization and according to Hasibuan (2017:119) compensation is all income in the form of money, direct or indirect goods received employees as compensation for services provided to the company. The establishment of a compensation system can be said to be effective because compensation is an important part of human resource management because it helps attract and retain talented jobs. In addition, the company's compensation system has an impact on strategic performance.

D. Work Discipline

According to (Hasibuan, 2019:444) work discipline is a person's awareness and willingness to comply with all company regulations and applicable social norms. Work discipline is a tool that managers use to communicate with employees so that they are willing to increase a person's awareness and willingness to fulfill all company regulations (Rivai, 2011: 825). Based on the definition above, it can be concluded that work discipline is an attitude of behavior and actions that are in accordance with written and unwritten regulations, and if they are violated there will be sanctions for the violation.

E. Work environment

According to Nitisemito (2015: 109), what is meant by work environment is everything that is around the worker and that can influence him in carrying out the assigned tasks. This opinion is reinforced by Ahyari (2015: 124) by saying that the work environment is an environment in which employees work, in which there are elements of the conditions in which the employee works. So it can be concluded that the work environment actually has a positive influence on employees.

F. Work motivation

According to Robbins (2016; 201) motivation is the willingness to carry out high efforts to achieve organizational goals which are conditioned by the ability of efforts to meet certain individual needs, whereas according to Hasibuan (in Febrianti, N.R 2020) work motivation is the provision of motivation that creates enthusiasm for work someone so that they are willing to work together, work effectively and be integrated with all efforts to achieve satisfaction with stimuli arising from within and without. This stimulation will create encouragement for someone to carry out activities.

G. Employee performance

According to Adhari (2020: 77), employee performance is the result produced by certain job functions or activities in certain jobs over a certain period of time, which shows the quality and quantity of the work. However, Rerung (2019:54) says that employee performance is behavior produced in tasks that can be observed and evaluated, where employee performance is the contribution made by an individual in achieving organizational goals, so that work results can be achieved by a person or group of people within An organization must be in accordance with its respective authorities and responsibilities in order to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally and without violating the law and in accordance with morals and ethics.

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III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Regarding the research context, problem formulation, literature review, and conceptual framework, then hypothesis that can be formed is as follows:

- H1: Compensation has a significant effect on employee performance at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H2: Work discipline has a significant effect on employee performance at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H3: Work environment has a significant effect on employee performance at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H4: Compensation has a significant effect on work motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H5: Work discipline has a significant effect on work motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H6: Work environment has a significant effect on work motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H7: Work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H8: Compensation has a significant effect on employee performance through work motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H9: Work discipline has a significant effect on employee performance through Work Motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.
- H10: Work environment has a significant effect on employee performance through work motivation at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area.

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

A. Data Types and Sources

This research uses a quantitative approach with research proposals, processes, hypotheses, going into the field, analyzing and concluding data through the results of questionnaires obtained from a predetermined population.

B. Population

Population is a generalized area which is usually in the form of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the author so that Sugiyono (2016:215) can study them and draw conclusions. The population in this study were all permanent employees at J&T Express in the Sampang Regency area, totaling 120 employees.

C. Data Collection

In (Robert K Yin, 2014) it is stated that research data collection can be carried out through four types of data collection techniques, namely interview techniques, observation, questionnaires and literature study. In this study, research data was collected through an interview process and questionnaires towards the board of directors of J&T Express for the Sampang Regency Region.

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D. Data Analysis Method

In this study, hypothesis testing was conducted utilizing a Structural Equation Model (SEM) with a Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. PLS is a type of component or variant-based structural equation model. The purpose of hypothesis testing was to ascertain whether there is a significant impact of the research variables on each other. This analysis involved examining the Regression Weight through Critical Ratio (CR) and Probability (P) values. The predetermined criteria for acceptance were a CR value of ≥ 1.96 and a P-value of ≤ 0.05 . If the results of data processing met these criteria, the research hypothesis under consideration was deemed valid.

V. RESULT & DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of Measurement Model/ Outer Model

Figure 2 Outer Model

To test *convergent validity* value is used *outer loading* and *Average Variant Extracted (AVE)*. An indicator is declared to be satisfactory *convergent validity* in the good category when value *outer loading* > 0.7 and value *Average Variant Extracted* > 0.5 . Here are the values *outer loading* and *Average Variant Extracted* of each indicator in this research variable:

Table. 1 Convergent Validity Test - Outer Loading

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Compensation (X1)	X1.1	0.735
	X1.2	0.753
	X1.3	0.769
	X1.4	0.825
	X1.5	0.818
	X1.6	0.713
Work Discipline (X2)	X2.1	0.719
	X2.2	0.711
	X2.3	0.832
	X2.4	0.770
	X2.5	0.748
	X2.7	0.733
Work Environment (X3)	X3.2	0.737
	X3.4	0.733
	X3.5	0.736
	X3.6	0.785

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Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading
Work Motivation (Z)	Z1	0.762
	Z2	0.710
	Z3	0.838
	Z4	0.789
	Z6	0.717
	Z7	0.806
	Employee Performance (Y)	Y3
Y4		0.756
Y6		0.758
Y9		0.765
Y10		0.749

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in table 1 above, it is known that each research variable indicator has many values *outer loading* > 0.7. An indicator is said to have good reliability, if the values *outer loading* above 0.7

Table. 2 Convergent Validity Test - Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	AVE
Compensation (X1)	0,593
Work Discipline (X2)	0,567
Work Environment (X3)	0,560
Work Motivation (Z)	0,595
Employee Performance (Y)	0,576

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in table 2 above, it is known that the value *Average Variant Extracted* all variables in this study were > 0.5. Thus it can be stated that each variable has *convergent validity* good. In the next section, the test results will be described *discriminant validity* using values *Fornell-Larcker* and *Cross Loading*. An indicator is declared to meet standards *discriminant validity* when value *Fornell-Larcker* and *Cross Loading* the indicator on the variable is the largest compared to the other variables. The following are the values *Fornell-Larcker* and *Cross Loading* each indicator:

Table. 3 Discriminant Validity Test - Fornell-Larcker

	X1	X2	X3	Z1	Y
Compensation (X1)	0.770				
Work Discipline (X2)	0.591	0.753			
Work Environment (X3)	0.553	0.686	0.748		
Work Motivation (Z)	0.723	0.553	0.528	0.772	
Employee Performance (Y)	0.643	0.494	0.489	0.714	0.759

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in table 3 above, it can be seen that *discriminant validity* have been fulfilled in compiling their respective variables where the construct indicators are not more strongly connected to other constructs than to their own constructs.

Table. 4 Discriminant Validity Test - Cross Loading

	C (X1)	WD (X2)	WE (X3)	WM (Z)	EP (Y)
X1.1	0.735	0.433	0.440	0.470	0.399
X1.2	0.753	0.447	0.408	0.415	0.461
X1.3	0.769	0.495	0.414	0.465	0.451
X1.4	0.825	0.504	0.415	0.613	0.496
X1.5	0.818	0.400	0.438	0.636	0.528
X1.6	0.713	0.454	0.434	0.658	0.586
X2.1	0.367	0.719	0.534	0.404	0.192
X2.2	0.377	0.711	0.359	0.361	0.181
X2.3	0.437	0.832	0.497	0.395	0.312
X2.4	0.424	0.770	0.595	0.453	0.456

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	C (X1)	WD (X2)	WE (X3)	WM (Z)	EP (Y)
X2.5	0.503	0.748	0.605	0.466	0.505
X2.7	0.515	0.733	0.443	0.388	0.441
X3.2	0.328	0.408	0.737	0.395	0.327
X3.4	0.445	0.519	0.733	0.346	0.383
X3.5	0.494	0.547	0.736	0.393	0.363
X3.6	0.389	0.573	0.785	0.441	0.390
Y10	0.470	0.336	0.349	0.641	0.749
Z1	0.574	0.485	0.492	0.762	0.516
Z2	0.439	0.385	0.386	0.710	0.508
Z3	0.592	0.488	0.455	0.838	0.590
Z4	0.626	0.430	0.406	0.789	0.551
Z6	0.569	0.398	0.377	0.717	0.565
Z7	0.528	0.366	0.321	0.806	0.571
Y3	0.522	0.476	0.445	0.589	0.766
Y4	0.481	0.353	0.416	0.450	0.756
Y6	0.573	0.382	0.327	0.519	0.758
Y9	0.372	0.310	0.310	0.476	0.765

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in table 4 above, it can be seen that each indicator of each construct has a higher loading on its own construct than on other constructs. So it can be stated that the indicators used in this research have *discriminant validity* who are good at arranging their respective variables.

This section is the test results *reliability* using value *composite reliability*, *rho_A*, and *Cronbach's alpha*. An indicator is declared to meet standards *reliability* when value *composite reliability value* > 0.6 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998; Chin & Dibbern, 2010), then the *rho_A* and *Cronbach's alpha* > 0.7. Here are the value *composite reliability*, *rho_A*, and *Cronbach's alpha* each indicator:

Table. 5 Reliability Test - Composite Reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach's Alpha

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability
Compensation (X1)	0.863	0.870	0.897
Work Discipline (X2)	0.850	0.860	0.887
Work Environment (X3)	0.738	0.741	0.836
Work Motivation (Z)	0.863	0.866	0.898
Employee Performance (Y)	0.817	0.820	0.872

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data presented in table 5 above, it can be seen that the value *composite reliability* all research variables are > 0.6, then the value of *rho_A* and *Cronbach's alpha* is > 0.7. These results indicate that each variable has met *composite reliability*, *rho_A*, and *Cronbach's alpha* so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

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B. Evaluation of Structural Model/ Inner Model

Figure 3 Inner Model

Evaluation *path coefficients* used to show how strong the effect or influence of exogenous variables is on endogenous variables. Based on the inner model scheme shown in Figure 3, it can be explained that the value *path coefficients* The largest influence of Compensation on Work Motivation is 16,411, then the influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance is 9,940, while the smallest influence is Work Discipline on Employee Performance of 0.662. Based on the results of this description, it shows that all the variables in this model have *path coefficients* with a positive number. This shows that the greater the value *path coefficients* on an exogenous variable on an endogenous variable, the stronger the influence.

Table. 6 R-Square

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Work Motivation (Z)	0,739	0,730
Employee Performance (Y)	0,697	0,689

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Based on the data in table 6 above, it can be seen that the R-value *Square Adjusted* for the variables Work Motivation and Employee Performance are respectively 0.730 and 0.689, which means the ability of the exogenous variable to explain the endogenous variable is 73% (Strong) and 69.7% (*moderate/medium*) where 27% and the remaining 30.3% are the influence of other exogenous variables not measured in this study.

Table. 7 Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Significant
Compensation (X1) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.221	0.221	0.052	4.237	0.000	Positive Significant
Work Discipline (X2) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.034	0.035	0.051	0.662	0.509	Not Significant
Work Environment (X3) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.085	0.084	0.044	1.935	0.054	Not Significant
Compensation (X1) → Work Motivation (Z)	0.582	0.581	0.035	16.411	0.000	Positive Significant
Work Discipline (X2) → Work Motivation (Z)	0.128	0.130	0.048	2.670	0.008	Positive Significant

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	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>T-Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>	<i>Significantsi</i>
Work Environment (X3) → Work Motivation (Z)	0.118	0.118	0.049	2.423	0.016	Positive Significant
Work Motivation (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.491	0.491	0.049	9.940	0.000	Positive Significant
Work Discipline (X2) → Work Motivation (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.286	0.285	0.034	8.519	0.000	Positive Significant
Work Environment (X3) → Work Motivation (Z) → Employee Performance (Y)	0.063	0.064	0.024	2.608	0.009	Positive Significant
Compensation (X1) → Work Motivation (Z) → Work Motivation (Z)	0.058	0.058	0.025	2.299	0.022	Positive Significant

Source: Data processed by Smart-PLS

Table 7 shows the results of the PLS calculation which states the influence between variables. Based on the table above, it can be seen that of the 10 hypotheses processed in this research, it can be declared accepted or significant if the P-value *Values* < 0.05 and *T-statistics* > 1.96. There are 2 hypotheses which state that the effect is not significant while the other 8 hypotheses state that it has a significant positive effect.

H1: Competency influences employee performance

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the first hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results showing a significant positive influence can be interpreted as higher compensation the higher/better the performance of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area, that is on the other hand, the lower the compensation the lower the performance of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area.

Specifically, increases or changes in the level of compensation received by employees were identified as factors that were statistically associated with improvements in their performance. These results indicate that J&T employees in the Sampang Regency region tend to achieve better performance when they receive a higher or more adequate level of compensation. Economic factors may be one of the main drivers behind this finding, where employees may be motivated to improve their performance in the hope of getting better compensation.

An organization's success in providing compensation commensurate with employee contributions can be considered an important factor in creating a productive work environment and supporting overall performance growth. These results support the hypothesis that better compensation can act as a positive driver of employee performance. Practical implications of these findings may include the importance of compensation management as a strategic tool in improving productivity and overall organizational performance.

H2: Work Discipline influences Employee Performance

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the second hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results which show an insignificant effect can be interpreted as a high or low level of work discipline has no effect on the performance of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area.

These results indicate that other factors outside work discipline have a more dominant role in shaping employee performance. Although work discipline is considered an important factor in achieving good results, the results of this study highlight the possibility of other variables that have a greater impact on employee performance. These findings may reflect the complexity and variation in the interpretation of the concept of work discipline. Work discipline does not only include obedience to rules and procedures, but also involves commitment to work, responsibility and efficiency in carrying out tasks.

Therefore, these findings can provide a basis for redefining or delving deeper into the dimensions and components of work discipline that may be more relevant to employee performance. In the context of a broader interpretation, these findings may indicate that a one-size-fits-all approach to work discipline management is not always effective. Individual differences and job roles may require management strategies that are more flexible and focused on the specific needs of employees and jobs. Developing a more contextual and individualized approach can help organizations to more effectively exploit employee performance potential.

H3: Work environment influences employee performance

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the third hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results which show an insignificant effect can be interpreted as the work environment Comfortable or conducive conditions are not always the main determinant of the success of J&T Express Sampang Regency employees in achieving optimal performance results.

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These results confirm that J&T Express tends to have a highly standardized work structure and pattern, where the work environment does not provide significant enough variation to influence employee performance. If the tasks given to employees are routine and clearly measurable, work environment factors may not be the dominant variable in determining performance. Perceptions of the work environment can vary between regions.

Employees in Sampang Regency have other factors that influence their performance more, such as local values, social expectations, or even personal motivation that are stronger than the influence of the work environment. Internal company factors such as human resource management policies, incentive systems, and performance appraisal mechanisms may also play a role in the results of such research. If J&T Express management places greater emphasis on other factors such as training, employee development, or reward systems, this can replace the influence of the work environment in determining performance.

H4: Competence influences work motivation

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the fourth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results showing a significant positive influence can be interpreted as higher compensation the higher the level of work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area, that is on the other hand, the lower the compensation the lower the level of work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area.

These findings highlight the important role of financial compensation in establishing higher levels of motivation among the workforce. It can be interpreted that higher financial compensation can be a major motivation driver for employees. Having clear financial rewards for good performance creates a direct link between employees' efforts and the rewards they receive, providing additional incentives for them to achieve top results. In this context, compensation is not only seen as a form of salary, but also as a tool to increase intrinsic motivation, where especially J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area feel their value is recognized and appreciated.

Increased motivation can be interpreted as a positive response to fair and transparent compensation policies. Employees who feel they are treated fairly in terms of compensation tend to have higher levels of work motivation because they see a direct connection between their contributions and the rewards they receive. Therefore, compensation policies that are transparent and based on performance can create an environment where employees feel motivated to continue performing at high levels.

H5: Work Discipline influences Work Motivation

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the fifth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results which show a significant positive influence can be interpreted as meaning that the higher the level of work discipline applied, the higher the level of work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency Region. On the other hand, if the level of work discipline decreases, it will tend to result in a decrease in work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area.

These results can be interpreted to mean that work discipline can act as a trigger for intrinsic motivation. Employees who have a high level of discipline tend to have a structured work routine, allowing them to achieve goals and objectives more consistently. Awareness of responsibility and regularity in carrying out daily tasks can build a sense of personal achievement and have a positive impact on employee intrinsic motivation.

The positive impact of discipline on work motivation can also be seen in relation to achieving career goals. Disciplined employees tend to have clear career plans and take concrete actions to achieve them. Awareness of the steps needed to achieve career goals can provide additional motivation for employees to work hard and remain focused on achieving these achievements. In this context, discipline is considered the foundation for stable productivity, which can be a source of motivation as employees see the results of their work efforts.

H6: Work environment influences work motivation

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the sixth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results which show a significant positive influence can be interpreted as meaning that the better the working environment conditions created, the higher the level of work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency Region. On the other hand, if the working environment conditions created are not good, it will tend to result in a decrease in work motivation of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area.

These results can be interpreted as a work environment that encourages collaboration, open communication, and joint achievement can create a sense of employee ownership and identification with organizational goals. In this context, employees can feel more deeply engaged in their work, creating higher levels of motivation as they feel the positive impact their contributions generate. In addition, positive employee relationships and team support can be important factors in forming work motivation.

A work environment that supports collaboration and team engagement can create a sense of community and support, which are key factors in establishing high levels of motivation. Having social support from colleagues and superiors can be an extra source of motivation, especially when facing complex challenges or projects. A work environment that provides sufficient resources, including

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technology, training, and infrastructure, can help employees complete their tasks more effectively. Comfortable work facilities that support employee well-being can also create conditions that support higher levels of motivation.

H7: Work Motivation influences employee performance

Based on the results of statistical tests carried out in this research, it was found that the seventh hypothesis was Accepted and Significant. The results which show a significant positive influence can be interpreted as meaning that the higher the level of work motivation, the higher/better the performance of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency Region, as follows. On the other hand, the lower the level of work motivation, the performance of J&T Express employees in the Sampang Regency area tends to decline.

These results indicate that work motivation is considered the main trigger that encourages employees to achieve higher levels of performance. Motivated employees have an internal drive to give their best in their tasks, creating a direct relationship between the level of motivation and the effort required to achieve better results. Intrinsic motivation, which arises from personal satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment, can be a powerful internal resource in improving the quality and quantity of performance.

This means that work motivation can influence employee orientation towards their goals and responsibilities. Employees who are positively motivated tend to be more focused and directed in achieving individual and organizational goals. They have the ability to identify priorities, overcome obstacles, and prioritize tasks effectively, ultimately contributing to improved overall performance. Work motivation can also create a positive cycle that strengthens performance. When employees feel a sense of success or accomplishment as a result of their motivated efforts, this can increase their self-confidence and job satisfaction.

H8: Competency influences employee performance

From table 5.7 above, the values can be seen that the original sample (O) is 0.286 which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-Values 0.000, which is below 0.05, which is the P-Values indicates that Compensation (X1) influences Employee Performance (Y) with Work Motivation (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the eighth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant.

Based on the results of the previous analysis, competence is also accepted and significant for employee performance, in this case the nature of work motivation as a mediator is Mediation. The mediation meant here is that the existence of work motivation as a mediator is expected because the existence of work motivation as a mediator can influence the influence between exogenous (compensation) and endogenous variables (employee performance). This states that the existence of constant work motivation means that compensation can improve employee performance.

The importance of work motivation as a mediator can be explained as a mechanism that explains how compensation indirectly influences employee performance through work motivation. In other words, high levels of compensation not only have a direct influence on improving performance, but also through increasing employee work motivation. With work motivation as a mediator, it can be concluded that employees who receive adequate compensation tend to have a high level of work motivation, and this motivation then positively influences the increase in their performance.

H9: Competency influences employee performance

From table 5.7 above, the values can be seen that the original sample (O) is 0.063 which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-Values 0.009, which is below 0.05, which is the P-Values indicates that Work Discipline (X2) influences Employee Performance (Y) with Work Motivation (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the tenth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant.

Based on the results of the previous analysis that work discipline is rejected and is not significant to employee performance, in this case the nature of work motivation as a mediator is Full Mediation. Full mediation, which is meant here, means that the existence of work motivation as a mediator is highly desirable because the presence of work motivation as a mediator can influence the influence between exogenous (work discipline) and endogenous variables (employee performance). This states that the presence of work motivation means that work discipline can improve employee performance.

This finding can be interpreted to mean that the level of work discipline applied in the organization may not have a direct impact on employee performance. However, through the influence of work motivation, work discipline can still act as a trigger to improve performance indirectly. In other words, employees who have a high level of work discipline may not immediately achieve better performance, but the work motivation resulting from this discipline is the main cause of increased performance. The results of this analysis provide valuable insight for company management to evaluate work discipline management strategies. Although work discipline has not been proven to have a direct influence on performance, understanding the full role of work motivation as a mediator can provide additional insight. Therefore, the company's focus can be shifted to strengthening work motivation through strategies to increase work discipline, with the hope that this will have a positive impact on employee performance.

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H10: Competency influences employee performance

From table 5.7 above, the values can be seen that the original sample (O) is 0.058 which states that the three variables have a positive influence. Then by looking at the P-values 0.022 which is below 0.05 which is the P-values indicates that the Work Environment (X3) influences Employee Performance (Y) with Work Motivation (Z) as a mediator. Based on the regression results, it can be concluded that the tenth hypothesis was Accepted and Significant.

Based on the results of the previous analysis that the work environment is rejected and not significant to employee performance, in this case the nature of work motivation as a mediator is Full Mediation. What is meant by full mediation here is that the existence of work motivation as a mediator is highly desirable because the presence of work motivation as a mediator can influence the influence between exogenous (work environment) and endogenous (employee performance) variables. This states that the existence of work motivation makes the work environment able to improve employee performance.

The interpretation of these results implies that directly, the work environment may not have a significant impact on improving employee performance. However, through the intermediary of work motivation, the work environment can still have an important role in motivating employees to achieve better performance. In other words, the quality of a positive and supportive work environment can provide encouragement to increase employee work motivation, which in turn influences their performance positively. In this context, company management can direct attention to efforts to improve and develop a motivating work environment. Although the work environment does not have a direct impact on performance, understanding the full role of work motivation as a mediator can help companies identify areas in the work environment that need to be improved to create conditions that are more conducive to increasing employee motivation and performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

Employees in Sampang Regency tend to achieve better performance when they receive higher compensation, emphasizing the strategic role of compensation management in improving organizational productivity. The concept of work discipline is complex, extending beyond rule obedience to encompass commitment, responsibility, and task efficiency, suggesting that a tailored approach to work discipline management is essential. Perceptions of the work environment may vary based on regional influences, with factors such as local values, social expectations, and personal motivation playing significant roles alongside internal company factors. Financial compensation emerges as a primary motivation driver for J&T Express employees in Sampang Regency, emphasizing the importance of a fair and transparent compensation policy to boost work motivation and create a positive relationship between employee contributions and rewards. A high level of work discipline acts as a trigger for intrinsic motivation, fostering a sense of personal achievement and positively influencing employees' intrinsic motivation. A collaborative and communicative work environment that promotes shared achievement fosters a sense of employee ownership and identification with organizational goals. Work motivation emerges as a crucial trigger for higher employee performance, highlighting its significance in achieving organizational objectives. The research identifies work motivation as a significant mediator between compensation and employee performance, indicating that employees with adequate compensation tend to exhibit high work motivation. Strengthening work motivation through strategies to enhance work discipline is suggested as a focus for the company, with the expectation that it will positively impact employee performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are suggestions from the author for further research based on our research results.

1. Companies can carry out in-depth evaluations of compensation policies, including salary structures and incentive systems.
2. Companies can consider efforts to improve and develop a motivating work environment to improve the quality of employee motivation and performance.
3. Employees may consider it because awareness of responsibility and order can have a positive impact on personal achievement and work motivation.
4. Employees can strive to be more engaged in their work and look for ways to increase their sense of ownership of the organization's goals.

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